

THE ROLE OF MARRIAGE MOTIVES IN STRENGTHENING FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS

Kayumova Guzal Narzullayevna

Researcher at Termiz State University

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Abstract

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to strengthening family and marital relationships. President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, in one of his speeches, emphasized: "The greatest happiness, and I will never tire of repeating this, is the peace of our families! The family is a small homeland; if the family is peaceful and happy, the homeland will be peaceful. May we all be blessed to witness those happy days and the prosperity of our youth and country!" The President has also noted that among young married couples, there are cases where family life is perceived superficially, without understanding the sacred nature of marriage. Unfortunately, divorces among young families are increasing due to trivial reasons, and innocent children are left without parental care and affection. This shows the relevance of ensuring family stability and the need for psychological research in this area.

Introduction

Despite the attention given to family stability in our country, various conflicts, misunderstandings, and divorces still occur. This necessitates a deeper psychological and sociological analysis of the reasons behind such issues. From early childhood, young people grow up listening to fairy tales about love and marriage, yet when they reach adulthood, many of them lack an adequate understanding of what real family life entails. To study attitudes toward marriage and the motives behind it, questionnaires and surveys are mainly used. In our research, we applied the "Marriage Motives" questionnaire developed by the Russian sociologist S. I. Golod, which is designed to identify the underlying motives for entering marriage.

Methodology

According to S. I. Golod, the leading motives for marriage include: love, shared values and interests, the feeling of loneliness, compassion, the desire for children, coincidence, material security, and the partner's possession of housing. Respondents were asked to choose and rank these eight motives in order of importance. For data analysis, we considered the total number of respondents who selected each motive in the first three ranks. A total of 60 university students participated in the study.

Table 1. Respondents' Indicators According to the "Marriage Motives"
Methodology

No.	Marriage Motives	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Partner's possession of housing	38	63.3
2	Desire for children	31	51.6
3	Love	28	46.6
4	Material security	23	38.3
5	Feeling of loneliness	21	35.0
6	Coincidence (random decision)	17	28.3
7	Compassion	15	25.0
8	Shared views and interests	8	13.3

Note: The table shows the dominant motives for marriage among respondents, based on the "Marriage Motives" methodology.

Marriage motives play a vital role in shaping marital relationships and in developing mutual attraction and emotional bonding between spouses. This emotional attraction is a complex process involving various psychological, cultural, and social factors. Uzbek psychologists such as M. Davletshin, G'. Shoumarov, E. G'oziyev, X. Karimov, N. Sog'inov, F. Akramova, G. Yadgarova, M. Salayeva, and D. Xoliqov have conducted research in this field. Similarly, social and pedagogical aspects of family life have been studied by V. N. Gurov, S. Nazarova, Yu. P. Azarov, Ye. P. Arnaumova, A. K. Zheleznova, T. V. Shelyag, and Uzbek scholars such as A. Munavvarov, T. X. Teshavoyeva, M. D. Savurov, and O. Musurmonova. Most of these studies examine family relationships within the context of Uzbek traditions and ethnopsychological characteristics. In our research, however, the focus was placed on the psychological nature, origins, and dynamics of marital relationships.

Conclusion

Statistical data show that legally and emotionally stable families are often those formed on traditional or socially expected grounds rather than purely romantic ones. Such couples, having married "like everyone else," tend to adapt to each

other over time, develop mutual understanding, care, and emotional closeness. While love-based marriages may seem ideal, they are not always the most stable. Families established on practical and socially balanced motives often develop strong emotional bonds over time, ensuring both legal and psychological stability within the marriage.

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